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Investigating the Wave and Sea-state Response to Wind Forcing

In the 21st century, cargo ships across the planet travel along only the most efficient routes, meaning any increase in the efficiency of a trans-oceanic route means an increase in profit and humanities' progress. Such modifications of the established routes are closely related to how wind forcing affects waves and sea state, since even the heaviest ships are no match for the forces of the ocean. The following analysis attempts to find and compare the most notable relationships between the independent variables: wind speed, wind direction, and the dependent variable: wave height. When analyzing aspects of the wind forcing, the independent variables mentioned may become dependent on either the latitude, longitude, or the complete geographic location. The first extensive research on this topic started in the mid 20th century, which is around when the main climatic models used to determine sea-state now were contrived. Predictive models such as the Pierson-Moskowitz spectrum help narrow down the direct impact of constant winds on wave heights, while more modern studies focus on wind gusts and their influence, generating an already comprehensive amount of information on this topic. While the primary research conducted for this analysis is not nearly as scientifically valuable as the hundreds of documents available with very similar information for the same regions, it still both underlines and counters different conclusions found in the previous, more qualified studies. The main premise of the log used is not so much to create new predictions for climatologic sea-state, but rather to check and validate the already existing ones.

Section One: Methodology

Of the data in the primary research conducted on the ship, not all variables were measured mechanically, and none of the measurements were conducted by certified personnel. While this does not completely discredit the value of the data, those aspects must be taken into consideration when analyzing and comparing the results to other studies. The wind speed was recorded on the Beaufort scale, a twelve-level scale used to record wind speeds at sea for hundreds of years. When analyzing the data, all the wind speed entries were converted into mean speeds, for example, the level 4 of the Beaufort scale is between 5.5 and 7.9 m/s, so for every reading of 4 in the ship log, the result was the mean of the interval, so $(5.5-7.9)/2 = 6.22$ m/s. The wind direction inside the log was recorded using standard direction approximations on a 32-step wind rose shown on the diagram below.

Every log entry was transformed into degrees as they are the SI unit of angle measure, meaning an entry of NbE would be transformed into 11.25° since $0^\circ + (360^\circ/32) = 11.25^\circ$. These numerical approximations are easier to graph mathematically for correlation, since a computer can understand them as basic units on an axis. The wave height was indicated in the log on an 8-level scale of approximate height. The ship had sensors that precisely measured wind speed, wind direction, and several other variables. The wave height, however, was left to possibly erroneous judgement of the student which was writing entries into the log. The data available

is still scientifically useful, as sea state is non-constant, meaning not every wave is the same, even at one instant, but it is less precise. The last variables noted were the latitude and longitude of the location of the entry, calculated by the ships GPS system; these being entered every four hours rather than every hour. All the data was afterwards quantified in electronic graphing software, to create multiple two-dimensional frequency tables.

Section Two: Wind-Wave Relationships

The first two, and arguably most important variables analyzed, are wave height vs. wind speed. While this relationship may initially seem trivial and obvious, the very intuitive more wind → large waves narrative isn't necessarily always correct. In oceanography and climatology, wave height isn't determined solely by wind speed, but rather by a combination of wind speed, direction, duration, wind fetch, and wave response time (Laurila). The first example of sea state not being linearly related to wind speed is sea swell, or crestless waves. Once the ocean experiences a stronger wind, the waves calm down much later than the weather conditions do. Some crestless waves stay in movement for up to a week, meaning any climatological predictions must account for ocean response time. Another, exactly opposite instance of a non-linear relationship between wind speed and wave height is the speed at which waves form: "In addition, wave climate depends on wind regimes and on land-sea distribution. In other words, waves need fetch to develop..." (Morales-Marquez). While the Atlantic Ocean is not at all a small basin, there is no standard formula for the time that wind must blow at a certain speed to create a wave of a certain height, since waves take time to form after being hit with strong winds. Sea state does not respond to the instantaneous increase in wind force but is instead dependent on the accumulation of the energy generated by the wind. Factors such as wind direction and wind stress also directly affect sea state; wind stress being the force exerted by the wind on the ocean surface that transfers momentum from the atmosphere to the water, driving wave formation. This means that quickly changing and non-linear wind directions don't

increase wave development. While these are the basic direct causes that influence general wave height and sea state, accurate climatological predictions are done by taking many other things into consideration. In addition to magnitude, the consistency of wind direction plays a significant role in wave development. Stable wind direction makes energy concentrated into one wave system, whereas rapidly shifting winds distribute energy across multiple directions, limiting wave growth.

An important aspect of the collected data that will be compared to the prior studies is the threshold of maximum wave height H_{\max} . Oceanic waves have a certain tolerance to height and depending on the water depth and geographic location; their crests collapse back on them at different maximum heights. While this is one of the instances of the threshold height, another one that is much more related to wind is the idea of how much energy applied by the wind can go into forming a wave. At a determined wave speed, "...the energy input from the air turbulence balances viscous dissipation in the water..." (Li), meaning the component of energy that the wave uses to generate greater height becomes equal to the magnitude of energy lost due to turbulent flow, inefficient energy transfer at high speeds, and even water heating. Waves at that point cannot grow any higher. This threshold is computed with a mathematical spectrum in a 1964 study by Pierson and Moskowitz, in which they calculated the formula that determines the wind speed U for which H_{\max} does not grow further: "...has deduced a number of properties of the spectrum from this analysis. The wave height must follow a U^2 law, for example. The law that $f_{\max} U/g = \text{constant}$ must also hold. If U_2 is greater than U_1 for fully developed seas, then $S(f, g, U_2) \geq S(f, g, U_1)$ for all f ." (Pierson). Since wave height follows a U^2 law, H is equal to U^2 , so for every increase in wind speed, the wave height increases by a square of that. Since there is a maximum wave frequency f_{\max} , as waves have a minimum length, the product of U and f_{\max} divided by earth's gravity g must always be a constant. This

means that for a certain maximum frequency and height, at a fully developed sea state, the energy of a wave is constant no matter the wind speed U .

Knowing all the factors in this relationship, and therefore the further limitations of the ship log data, its results can now be analyzed. To determine the first and most basic relation between wind speed and wave height, a graph was set up of the wave heights as the dependent variable over the average converted wind speed as the independent variable:

This, as expected, showed a rather positive relationship, though a coefficient of determination reading of ~ 0.56 shows some outliers imply the phenomenon of sea swell, the activeness of sea state in little to no wind. The coefficient of determination R^2 indicates a moderate correlation between wind speed and sea state, meaning that approximately 56% of the variability in wave height can be explained by wind speed alone. The remaining unexplained variance suggests the importance of additional factors: wind duration, directional stability, and prior sea conditions. An important factor to consider is the response time of the ocean, since the instant a constant and powerful wind hits the water is hours before the waves respond to it. To account

for this, I made another graph, where each wind speed entry was paired with a wave height entry from 6 hours later:

Contrary to what is expected, the value of the least square regression for this set of data and other ones with different time delays are all smaller than for the original one, suggesting that the relationship between wind speed and sea state cannot be properly described using a single fixed time delay. Instead, wave development is dependent on cumulative wind forcing over extended periods, as well as prior conditions. This aligns with the theoretical models of wave growth mentioned prior to this, which describe the ocean surface as a system in which energy accumulates gradually rather than responding to instantaneous wind input. Additionally, the use of a linear regression may underestimate this seemingly simple relationship, as theoretical models such as the ones by Pierson and Moskowitz suggest a nonlinear dependence of wave height on wind speed, or one approximately proportional to U^2 in fully developed sea conditions (Pierson).

The next way I analyzed these two variables was by comparing the maximum wave height during a certain time interval in which the wind speed never dropped below 6 m/s. The aim was to check whether prolonged constant wind generates more wind stress than a shorter gust.

While the data available was not as large as for the previous graphs, many of the points overlapped, showing a constant maximum wave height for the same duration of hours with strong wind. In one case, however, the wave height did not exceed 3 on the 8-level scale of approximate height, meaning the waves were under 1 meter for the entirety of two days during which the wind speed was constantly at least 6 m/s. This outlier yet again hints at the presence of wave generating factors that might seem secondary but, make up more than half of the reason why sea state increases. An example of such a factor is seasonality: "Seasonality accounts for 50% of the extreme wave height variability in the North Atlantic Ocean and up to 70% in some areas of the Mediterranean Sea. Once seasonality is filtered out, the North Atlantic Oscillation and the Scandinavian index are the dominant large-scale atmospheric patterns that control..." (Morales-Márquez). For this variable, the primary research conducted is insufficient to check

the claim of this paper, as the data collected on the ship was only during a 6-week period. This suggests that short-term observations may not capture the full variability of wave behavior, as longer climatic cycles influence wave formation over extended periods. Additionally, energy dissipation processes may prevent waves from continuing to grow, even under constant wind conditions. This aligns with the concept of a fully developed sea described by Pierson and Moskowitz, where wave growth reaches an equilibrium state and no longer increases despite continued wind forcing.

The next variables analyzed were Sea state and Wave Speed in time:

The time-series graph supports the concept of delayed wave response more than the previous data, as increases in wind speed are not immediately followed by increases in sea state.

Instead, wave height appears to peak after slightly longer periods of elevated wind, underlining that wave growth depends on cumulative energy input and not instant wind forcing. This data, however, still does not show any constant time lag, which aligns with: “...role of long-term processes, involving ocean adjustments at longer timescales (e.g. ocean gyres, deep ocean circulation) ...” (Voltaire 3482). This demonstrates that interactions

between wind forcing and ocean response occur over variable timescales rather than instantaneously. Additionally, processes such as subsurface wave dynamics further support the idea that ocean response is not instantaneous but distributed over time, consistent with the finding that “subsurface advection of water from the equator... influences surface conditions” (Voldoire 3481; Specht). The gradual increase in sea state during sustained wind in the data above illustrates the transition from a developing sea to a fully developed wave system, consistent with duration-limited growth described in oceanographic models. A more mature wave system also much more strictly follows the $H = U^2$ law, which again is consistent with the latter half of the time-series that includes sea state and wind speed. Several points in the data also show a lack of direct causation between wind and wave height, reinforcing the role of additional factors such as wind duration, seasonality, prior sea conditions, and wind direction. These observations align with theoretical models of wave growth, which describe the ocean surface as a system governed by cumulative forcing.

Further proof of this is seen in a graph of combined variables, in this case sea-state vs. wind speed and duration.

Combining these two variables into one framework yields a much clearer pattern than each of the variables individually. While wind speed alone showed a fairly small correlation with wave height, adding duration shows the cumulative and complex nature of wind forcing. Periods of time during which moderate/strong wind was sustained over longer durations clearly produce higher sea states than short bursts of much stronger wind. This underlines the idea that the ocean is more influenced by the sum of energy input over time and does not respond proportionally to any single variable. In multiple instances within the dataset, wind speeds of approximately 6-7 m/s sustained over longer periods of time produced wave heights comparable to or greater than those generated by winds of ~9 m/s that did not last as long. This suggests that duration acts as a multiplier in the energy transfer, making even moderate strength winds generate significant wave systems when given enough time.

This observation aligns closely with theoretical ideas of wave growth, especially the concept of the waves being limited by duration. For this concept, wave height is not constrained by any fetch, rather it is stopped by the length of time over which wind energy is applied. This

means the dataset is consistent with the ocean conditions rarely reflecting instantaneous relationships.

Latitude effect on Wave Height

Yet another incredibly important relationship observed in the dataset is between latitude and wave height.

Unlike wind speed, which directly transfers energy into the ocean surface, latitude influences atmospheric patterns and ocean currents. This means that analyzing wave height against latitude generates large insight into the broader climatic mechanisms in play with sea-state. The graph shows a non-linear and slightly clustered relationship between latitude and wave height. Higher wave heights such as 3 and 4 on the 8-level scale appear most frequently within mid-latitude ranges, while lower wave heights appear at lower latitudes.

This distribution suggests that wave energy is not uniformly distributed across latitudes but instead concentrated in areas where the climatic conditions work better with sustained winds. An explanation for this is connected to the fact that mid-latitudes are

dominated by westerly winds, which are usually stronger and more consistent than equatorial winds. These westerly winds generate longer wave systems, which is again consistent with the higher wave heights in the mid-latitudes that can be found on the graph. In contrast, equatorial regions often experience more stable but weaker winds, resulting in lower wave energy no matter how continuous the wind is. The variability seen in the graph, or all the regions where different latitudes produce the same wave heights, indicates that latitude alone just like any other variable cannot determine the outcome. Instead, it is connected to other variables. This supports the argument described earlier regarding wave formation being governed by a combination of factors rather than a single dominant one. The findings are also consistent with larger scale climatological studies. Morales-Márquez highlights that wave variability in the North Atlantic is strongly influenced by atmospheric patterns such as the North Atlantic Oscillation, which changes with latitude and affects wind across different regions. This helps explain why even in a narrow latitude range, wave heights in the dataset can vary greatly.

Wind Direction

Wind direction is another important factor in determining how energy is transferred into wave systems. The results of the data collected on the ship show that stable wind direction is almost linearly proportional to higher wave heights, even when wind speeds are similar for different directions. This means a wind of 6m/s that would blow in one direction for 5 hours will create larger waves than a wind of 12m/s blowing for 1 hour. This occurs because a consistent wind direction allows energy to add up within a single wave system, increasing wave amplitude. In contrast, changing wind directions distribute energy across multiple fronts, greatly reducing the efficiency of wave growth. The energy becomes separated and fragmented, which leads to lower overall wave heights. This idea explains the

outliers in the dataset where moderate to strong winds did not yield corresponding large waves.

This observation aligns with the previously analyzed principles that govern the ocean. Wind stress is most effective when it is applied in one direction, maximizing momentum transfer. When the direction is not stable, interference between wave systems can occur which in turn limits wave amplitude. Another important factor is considering angular deviation as a measurable variable. By calculating the change in wind direction between continuous measurements, it is possible to express directional stability as a mathematical variable. Periods with low average angular deviation correspond strongly with increased wave height, again supporting the idea that stability is a key component of wave growth. Periods where the change in wind direction exceeds $\sim 30^\circ$ show reduced wave heights, even with large wind speeds. This shows that other than directional change, magnitude is also critical in calculating energy transfer. Directional stability also has an effect on interference patterns of waves. When multiple waves are in the same direction, constructive interference can be present, meaning one wave overlaps with another one to create a larger 'super positioned' wave, increasing overall wave height. When, however, multiple wave systems intersect at different angles, destructive interference can happen, meaning one wave can cancel another one out, in turn reducing wave amplitude. This also explains why areas with highly different wind directions are often chaotic wave-wise. This was indirectly observed in the dataset through differences in wave height despite similar wind forcing.

Another factor that plays a role in forming waves is the relationship between wind direction and fetch direction. Even if wind direction is stable, the number of waves it generates depends on whether it is aligned with a long stretch of ocean, or long fetch. Winds blowing parallel to a coastline may have a smaller fetch, again generating a smaller wave

height. In contrast, winds directed across a stretch of open ocean maximize fetch and therefore wave growth as well. This further complicates the relationship, underlining the need for multi-variable analysis. While latitude provides great insight into the topic, the longitude introduces regional variability related to basin structure, proximity to land, and current systems. When wave height was plotted against longitude, the relationship appeared scattered; however, grouping data by longitudinal ranges revealed patterns linked to oceanic regions. In areas farther from continents, wave heights are often higher, suggesting the importance of fetch. Open ocean regions let waves develop fully, while proximity of land disrupts wave formation and reduces maximum height. This supports the idea that wave growth depends not only on wind speed and duration but also on the space in which it is happening. Even strong winds cannot generate large waves if the fetch is not sufficient. This means the dataset shows different atmospheric influences.

Expanding this, different longitudes of the Atlantic Ocean are influenced by different atmospheric systems, such as storm tracks. These systems affect both wind intensity and consistency, influencing wave height indirectly. Regions in dominant storm tracks are usually more likely to experience prolonged high winds, leading to increased wave energy. In contrast, areas under stable high-pressure systems may have weaker winds, that in turn yielding calmer sea states. Yet another variable derived from the collected data is how much wind speed fluctuates over time. This is called wind variability and examines the range and standard deviation of wind speeds in a single time constraint to provide additional information.

The analysis shows that steady winds produce larger waves than variable winds, even with similar average speeds. This is due to the fact that consistent wind lets energy transfer constantly, while variable wind does not. Sudden drops in wind speed interfere with wave growth, preventing their formation. To measure this effect, the standard deviation of winds in 6-hour time periods was considered. Periods with low standard deviation corresponded with higher wave heights, while high variability produced weaker wave development. This demonstrates that variability reduces the total amount of energy transferred into the ocean.

Gustiness also introduces short bursts of energy that are not sufficient for any change in wave height. Wave forming requires constant forcing to grow, meaning that a brief increase in wind speed will contribute much less to the overall energy that goes into waves than prolonged moderate winds. This explains why the graphs that include frequent gusts but no constant wind show a weaker causation between wind speed and wave height. This finding aligns with the research that describes wind as uniform masses instead of individual measurements. In his study, Salvacao highlights how wind consistency influences energy transfer, especially in the context of wind energy (Salvacao). While his focus is more on power output,

similar ideas to the ones he describes apply to wave formation; meaning stability enhances the effects.

Ocean Currents

Although this quantity was not measured by the students on the ship, the effect of ocean currents can be calculated through the inconsistencies in the main wave-height-wind-speed relationship. In multiple cases, similar wind speeds and durations produced different wave heights at different locations, clearly showing an additional variable, that being the currents. Ocean currents interact with wind-driven waves in such a way that when currents move in the same direction as the wind, wave growth is enhanced due to the previously mentioned constructive interference, or in this case increased relative velocity between air and water. Opposing currents on the other hand can reduce wave height by interrupting wave formation. This interaction is particularly relevant near the equator, which is where most of the data was collected, since that is where strong current systems exist. Wyrski's study on equatorial currents shows how closely linked water movement is in forming waves (Wyrski). The primary data supports this, since lower wave heights at certain latitudes may reflect the destructive interference of currents. Beyond having different effects on waves with changes in direction, currents also influence wave breaking. Opposing currents shorten the waves, making them break earlier, this in turn limiting their maximum height. Following currents, however, lengthen waves, meaning they travel further and maintain the same energy on a longer distance. This can result in larger sea swells long after wind speed decreases. Currents also contribute to energy coming back into the ocean. Energy can be transported through current systems, meaning certain conditions can affect waves in distant regions. This is connected to the explanation of cases where wave height continues to be high even with a reduced wind speed, underlining the concept of delayed ocean response.

Another important dimension of the data is the time of cycles for wind activity. While the dataset spans only six weeks, some patterns are still present. Previous graphs show some periods of consistently higher wave heights clustered together. These patterns may correspond to larger climatic cycles such as pressure oscillations. In his study, [Crespo](#) describes how oscillatory systems like the Atlantic Niño influence wind patterns across different longitudes. Although most of the primary data is far too limited to directly identify such types of cycles, even basic clustered wave activity suggests their presence. Additionally, clustering may also reflect the passage of larger synoptic-scale weather systems, such as cyclones or fronts ([Sherriff-Tadano](#); [Vecchi](#)). These weather systems generate sustained wind patterns over large enough areas to produce complete wave systems that stay for prolonged periods of time after the system has passed. The clustering found on most of the graphs that include wave height is consistent with such events.

Connection of the Findings

Combining all variables analyzed, a quite consistent conclusion can be derived:

Wave height is not controlled by any single factor, but by the interaction of multiple variables operating over time. Wind speed provides the biggest part of the energy input, but its effect is determined by duration, direction, and several other conditions. Latitude and longitude also influence the background conditions under which waves form, while temporal systems determine exactly how the wave-forming energy accumulates. The primary data strongly supports the idea of cumulative forcing, in which wave systems develop slowly through sustained energy input, rather than instantaneously. This also explains why simple

linear models cannot fully describe the relationship between wind and waves, and why more complex models are necessary. It becomes evident that each variable plays its own but, for the most part, an equally important role. Wind speed determines the potential energy input; duration controls how much of that potential is used, and both direction and geographic factors moderate the efficiency of the energy transfer. Variability is a limiting factor, while currents and temporal systems modify the outcome. The extremely complex interaction of these, and probably even more variables creates a system that is inherently nonlinear, making precise prediction very challenging.

The findings of this analysis have direct implications for maritime navigation. Since wave height depends on cumulative and regional factors, predicting sea-state requires more than just current wind conditions. Ships must account for prior weather patterns, geographic location, and expected wind stability. Routes optimized solely based on instantaneous wind data may miscalculate wave conditions, leading to increased risk and reduced efficiency. Using multi-variable models that consider duration, direction, and geographic factors can improve route planning. Additionally, these findings underline the importance of a predictive approach when using modern navigation systems. By using both real-time and historical data in forecasting, it becomes possible to better estimate future sea-state. This improves both efficiency and safety and reduces the likelihood of encountering unexpected waves.

Conclusion

This investigation set out to analyze the relationship between wind forcing and sea-state using primary data collected aboard a ship. While limited in scope, the dataset shows many insights that align with previously established theories. Wave height is influenced by a

combination of wind speed, duration, and direction, as well as geographic factors. The analysis shows that wave systems respond to cumulative energy input rather than instantaneous conditions, resulting in delayed and often complex responses.

The inclusion of latitude-based analysis also underlines the importance of large-scale patterns in shaping wave height. Mid-latitude regions show higher wave energy due to strong and consistent winds, while equatorial regions show smaller wave heights despite continuous wind presence. The analysis shows the incredibly large complexity of ocean systems and the need for multi-variable approaches in all applications. While the dataset does not provide any new conclusions, it validates the theoretical models.

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